

Bambooscape: Designing A Practice Of Rural Futures Through Bamboo Architecture And Spatial Design

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Abstract

Re:public Inc. has been leading the Satsuma Future Commons (SFC) project in Satsumasendai City since 2019, aiming to co-create sustainable futures for cities through cross-sector collaboration based on Circular Design principles. Our BambooScape project focuses on repurposing abandoned bamboo forests and creating new structures using bamboo resources. This paper explores the importance of the project in fostering a sustainable city. Japan has seen a significant growth of bamboo forests, posing challenges such as increased disaster risks and negative impacts on agriculture, forestry, and the environment. Recognizing the potential of bamboo, our team conducted research and engaged stakeholders to address the issue in Satsumasendai. Bamboo, known for its fertility, rapid growth, and sustainability, has a history of use in traditional Japanese architecture. Its resurgence offers opportunities for affordable housing, community spaces, and agricultural structures. Through showcasing bamboo's versatility and collaborating with stakeholders, we aim to revitalize the local economy and promote ecological balance. Our paper envisions a harmonious integration of nature and humanity, cultivating a regenerative local economy through bamboo-based architecture and participatory spatial design. By utilizing bamboo as a sustainable resource and collaborating with the community, BambooScape strives to create a positive impact on Satsumasendai's economy and environment.

Keywords

Regenerative design, Nature positive, Circular Design

1 Satsuma Future Commons and the “Bambooscape project”

The Satsuma Future Commons (SFC) project, situated in Satsumasendai City, Kagoshima prefecture, represents a visionary endeavor focused on co-creating sustainable futures for cities by embracing Circular Design principles. SFC serves as a civic innovation hub, fostering collaboration among diverse stakeholders, including citizens, researchers, designers, and local authorities, to devise innovative solutions. At its core, SFC seeks to address global challenges through the implementation of regenerative design and nature-positive approaches. An integral component of the SFC project is the BambooScape initiative, which holds immense importance in the pursuit of sustainable and regenerative practices. BambooScape harnesses the potential of bamboo architecture and spatial design to promote ecological balance and minimize environmental impact. This project recognizes the urgency to transition to circular economies and embrace nature-positive solutions, not only to meet the local community's needs but also to contribute to global sustainability efforts. By incorporating bamboo as a primary building material, the BambooScape project aligns with the principles of Circular Design, optimizing resource use, waste reduction, and ecosystem health. The rapid growth, versatility, and sustainable properties of bamboo make it an ideal choice for regenerative design practices. BambooScape aims to demonstrate the potential of bamboo in addressing global challenges and serve as a model for other cities striving for sustainable development.

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Through the BambooScape project, the SFC initiative revitalizes the local economy while contributing to the discourse on regenerative design and nature-positive approaches. By showcasing the transformative power of sustainable architecture and spatial design, the project paves the way for envisioning and co-creating cities that harmoniously integrate nature and humanity. Insights gained from BambooScape's implementation highlight the importance of collaboration, community engagement, and sustainable resource management in effective regenerative design. The concept of "Bambooscape" embodies the integration of bamboo within the landscape and urban environment, creating a unique fusion of nature and architecture. It goes beyond traditional architectural practices by recognizing bamboo's qualities as a versatile and eco-friendly material. The project envisions a network of bamboo structures, landscapes, and community spaces seamlessly blending into their surroundings, redefining the concept of urban and natural environments (fig 1). In the following sections of this paper, we delve deeper into the specific aspects of the BambooScape project, exploring its implications for regenerative design, nature-based solutions, urban green spaces, sustainable forest management, and the principles of the circular economy. By examining these dimensions, we shed light on how this project contributes to the broader goal of co-creating sustainable futures for cities, both in Satsumasendai City and within the global context of addressing pressing environmental challenges.

Figure 1: The Key Aspects of the Bambooscape Project

In the center is a map of Satsumasendai City and its surroundings, with pink representing the urban cityscape and green representing the natural landscape. Surrounding the map are 12 icons, with pink representing elements related to the city environment and green representing connections to the land and nature. The infographic visually represents the integration of bamboo in the urban and natural landscapes, highlighting the project's holistic approach towards creating a sustainable BambooScape in Satsumasendai City.

2 The Issue of Abandoned Bamboo Forests in Kagoshima Prefecture

Kagoshima Prefecture, with the largest area of bamboo groves in Japan, faces a pressing issue of increasing abandoned bamboo groves that pose various risks, including the potential for disasters. The shallow roots of bamboo make its unattended growth a risk factor for disasters such as landslides. In fact, a few years ago, Kagoshima Prefecture experienced a landslide caused by a collapsed slope in a bamboo grove, which blocked a highway (fig 2). According to the Forestry Agency, the total area of such forests in Japan was some 167,000 hectares in 2017, an increase of about 5,000 hectares from five years earlier. Kagoshima Prefecture alone accounts for approximately 18,000 hectares of these bamboo forests, making it the largest among the country's 47 prefectures (fig 3). These neglected groves are not adequately managed, exacerbating the risks, particularly landslides. Furthermore, considering the potential distribution of forests in the future, it becomes evident that Kyushu Island, and particularly Kagoshima Prefecture, have a significant probability of further developing this issue (fig 4).

Figure 2: Landslide in a Bamboo Grove Blocking a Highway

(Source: NHK Obtained on August 2022) <https://www.nhk.or.jp/kagoshima/lreport/article/000/39/>

Figure 3: Left - Bamboo Forest Area and Distribution as of March 2012, Right - Prefectures with High Bamboo Forest Area. (Source: Forestry Agency)

Figure 4: Potential Distribution of bamboo forest
 (Source: Takashi Someya, Shion Takemura, Shun Miyamoto, Mahito Kamada, "Predictions of bamboo forest distribution and associated environmental factors in Japan, using natural environmental information GIS and digital national land information")

In the context of abundant bamboo resources and uncontrolled growth near human settlements and infrastructure, sustainable forest management plays a crucial role in ensuring the long-term viability of bamboo resources and maintaining ecological balance. The BambooScape project recognizes the importance of sustainable forest management and incorporates various strategies to effectively address these challenges. One key strategy is the assessment and mapping of bamboo forests, which provides a comprehensive understanding of their distribution, density, and health. This information serves as the foundation for developing appropriate management plans and interventions. Mapping the bamboo

forests also helps identify areas where uncontrolled growth poses risks to human settlements and infrastructure, enabling targeted management actions. Resource utilization is another vital aspect of sustainable forest management. The BambooScape project focuses on repurposing abandoned bamboo forests and utilizing bamboo resources responsibly and efficiently. By transforming neglected areas into functional community spaces and structures, the project ensures that bamboo resources are utilized for the benefit of the local community while minimizing waste and environmental impact. Controlled harvesting and thinning are essential practices in sustainable forest management. Rather than eradicating bamboo growth entirely, controlled harvesting involves selectively removing mature bamboo culms while allowing younger shoots to grow and replenish the forest. This practice ensures a sustainable supply of bamboo resources while maintaining the integrity of the ecosystem. Thinning, on the other hand, involves removing excess or overcrowded bamboo to promote healthy growth and reduce the risk of fire and pests. Sustainable harvesting practices further contribute to the long-term viability of bamboo resources. These practices involve careful consideration of the bamboo's growth cycle, ensuring that only mature culms are harvested. By following sustainable harvesting techniques, such as selective cutting and leaving behind enough culms for regeneration, the BambooScape project promotes the resilience and regeneration of bamboo forests. Biodiversity conservation is an integral component of sustainable forest management. Bamboo forests provide habitats for various species, including plants, animals, and insects. The BambooScape project incorporates measures to protect and enhance biodiversity within bamboo forests, such as preserving understory vegetation and creating wildlife corridors. These efforts contribute to maintaining ecological balance and supporting the overall health of the ecosystem. Community engagement is crucial for the success of sustainable forest management. The BambooScape project actively involves local communities in decision-making processes and encourages their participation in bamboo forest management. By fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility among community members, the project promotes sustainable practices and ensures the long-term viability of bamboo resources. Community engagement also enables knowledge sharing and the preservation of traditional bamboo-related practices, strengthening the cultural and social significance of bamboo forests. In Satsumasendai, efforts are being made to address the issue of abandoned bamboo forests. However, the current approach is proving insufficient and unsustainable. Pictures highlighting the challenges associated with managing these forests serve as visual evidence. One common practice involves individuals entering the forest to cut excess bamboo culms, which are then burned. This method not only contributes to environmental degradation but also fails to provide a long-term solution (Fig 5).

Figure 5: Depiction of the unsustainable practice of cutting and burning bamboo to reduce the number of culms in abandoned forests, leading to the release of CO₂ emissions and environmental degradation. (Source: Re:public Inc.)

Another current management approach in Satsumasendai involves individuals bringing bamboo from their own properties to the nearest wood facility (Fig 6). However, the sheer quantity of bamboo presents a significant challenge, making effective management difficult. This situation emphasizes the urgent need

for more comprehensive and sustainable strategies to address the issue of abandoned bamboo forests in Satsumasendai. The existing practices, including the overwhelming amount of bamboo (Fig 7) and the burning of excess culms, demonstrate the limitations of the current approach and highlight the necessity for more effective solutions.

Figure 6: Individuals bringing bamboo from their own properties to the nearest wood facility for processing and disposal. (Source: Re:public Inc.)

Figure 7: Illustration depicting the overwhelming amount of bamboo accumulated in the wood facility, showcasing the continuous influx of bamboo brought by people on a daily basis. (Source: Re:public Inc.)

Sustainable forest management is essential for addressing the challenges posed by abundant bamboo resources and uncontrolled growth near human settlements and infrastructure. The BambooScape project incorporates strategies such as assessment and mapping, resource utilization, controlled harvesting and thinning, sustainable harvesting practices, biodiversity conservation, and community engagement to ensure the long-term viability of bamboo resources and maintain ecological balance. By implementing these strategies, the project aims to create a harmonious coexistence between humans and bamboo forests while promoting sustainable development.

3 Bamboo as a Building Material and Regenerative Design

Bamboo, renowned for its rapid growth and sustainability, plays a central role in the regenerative design practices of the BambooScape project. Its exceptional growth rate and ability to regenerate quickly make bamboo a renewable resource that can be harvested without depleting the ecosystem. Unlike resource-intensive materials such as steel and concrete, bamboo has a lower carbon footprint and requires less energy for processing and transportation. Apart from its environmental benefits, bamboo offers numerous ecological advantages when used in architecture and spatial design. Bamboo forests serve as valuable habitats for biodiversity, providing shelter and sustenance for various species. Incorporating bamboo into the built environment, the BambooScape project actively supports the health and resilience of local ecosystems. In ancient Japan, bamboo was widely used in architecture (Fig 7). However, contemporary architectural norms and restrictions pose challenges for local architects in expressing themselves creatively using bamboo. These restrictions limit the utilization of bamboo's unique qualities in modern construction, hindering the exploration of sustainable and regenerative design possibilities. Bamboo exhibits remarkable compressive strength, averaging around 14,000 pounds per square inch (psi). In comparison, concrete, a widely used building material, typically has a compressive strength of about 2,500 psi. This demonstrates that bamboo is significantly stronger in compression. When considering tensile strength, bamboo also proves itself as a formidable material. With an average tensile strength of approximately 1,400 psi, bamboo surpasses the tensile strength of many conventional building materials. In contrast, concrete typically has a much lower tensile strength, measuring around 300 psi. (Fig 8) Bamboo possesses structural properties that make it a versatile and sustainable building material. Its flexibility, strength, and lightweight nature allow for innovative architectural designs and construction techniques. Bamboo can be employed in the construction of pavilions, housing, and community spaces, showcasing the aesthetic appeal and functionality of regenerative design.

Figure 8: Traditional Japanese houses extensively utilized bamboo materials (Source: Masatoshi Watanabe / Bamboo Culture Promotion Association Specialist Revised on July 20, 2020.)

Figure 9: Infographic comparing the strength of bamboo to other building materials (Source: Data Charted from Jansen, 2020).

Regenerative design, as embraced by the BambooScape project, is a holistic approach that aims to minimize environmental impact while actively contributing to the health and vitality of ecosystems. Going beyond sustainability, regenerative design strives to restore, renew, and regenerate natural systems (Dumitrescu et al., 2023). The project applies regenerative design principles in various ways, such as repurposing abandoned bamboo forests to address overgrowth near houses and roads. This approach minimizes the need for new construction materials, reduces waste, and contributes to habitat preservation and ecosystem restoration. Bamboo architecture has gained momentum as a trend in Southeast Asia. Gupta and Kumar (2008) discuss the potential of bamboo in sustainable development, highlighting bamboo housing as a prominent application. Bamboo poles possess high strength in tension and compression, with a compressive strength roughly twice that of concrete and a tensile strength-to-weight ratio comparable to steel. Traditional houses, bahareque bamboo houses, and modern prefabricated houses made from bamboo laminated boards, veneers, and panels are the three main types of bamboo housing. Traditional bamboo houses are affordable, lightweight, strong, and earthquake-resistant, making them preferable to brick or cement constructions. Prefabricated houses made of engineered bamboo offer advantages such as ease of transportation and eco-friendliness. Moreover, prominent examples of bamboo architecture include Vo Trong Nghia Architects in Vietnam and the Bamboo U project in Bali, Indonesia. These examples showcase the innovative and sustainable use of bamboo in architectural design, further emphasizing its potential for regenerative and environmentally conscious construction. In summary, bamboo's rapid growth, sustainability, and structural properties make it an ideal building material for regenerative design. Despite challenges posed by contemporary architectural norms, bamboo offers significant ecological benefits, such as carbon sequestration, biodiversity support, and reduced resource consumption. By embracing bamboo as a versatile and renewable resource, the BambooScape project aims to contribute to sustainable and regenerative architecture while inspiring creativity and innovation in the field.

3.1 Exploring Bamboo Architecture: Student Engagement and Prototyping

The SFC project, in collaboration with Kyushu University and bamboo architecture expert Professor Iwamoto, has made significant strides in bamboo architecture within the BambooScape project in the last year. One notable aspect of this progress is the active involvement of students who come to Satsumasendai to study and immerse themselves in the world of bamboo. Throughout the workshops and

training programs, we and the students have the opportunity to explore the potential of bamboo as a sustainable building material. Our venture into the bamboo forests, gaining hands-on experience and learning about its unique characteristics and structural properties. The students' enthusiasm and dedication are evident as they engage in practical learning experiences (Fig 10). During our studies with the students, we embark on various prototype projects to understand the flexibility and versatility of bamboo. We experiment with different assembly techniques and observe how bamboo responds to different loads and forces. These prototypes allow the students to gain valuable insights into the material's behavior and potential applications (Fig 11). To overcome the challenges posed by bamboo's irregular nature, we work alongside experts and carpenters, delving into 3D model studies, focusing on analyzing the intricate joints, beams, and pillars required for structural stability and aesthetic appeal. These studies help refine our designs, ensuring weight distribution, connection methods, and overall architectural harmony (Fig 12). The culmination of our efforts is the realization of a final project—a tangible shelter constructed entirely from bamboo. Guided by experts and collaborating with local carpenters, the students showcase their ingenuity and the potential of bamboo architecture, employing innovative approaches, such as the "bundle pillars" and "bundle beams" structural system, which address the irregularities of bamboo culms (Fig 13). Once the shelter is complete, the project concludes with a series of events and exhibitions to showcase the achievements of bamboo architecture to the local community and beyond. Visitors have the opportunity to engage with the shelter, appreciating its aesthetic beauty and sustainable qualities. These events serve as a platform to inspire and foster a greater understanding of bamboo's potential in construction (Fig 14).

Through these workshops and collaborative efforts, the BambooScape project not only advances the field of bamboo architecture but also nurtures a deep appreciation for the sustainable potential of bamboo among the students. Their journey represents a transformative experience, where knowledge, creativity, and practical engagement converge to shape a future where bamboo becomes a prominent and environmentally friendly material in construction and design.

Figure 10: Students Engaging with Bamboo: Learning amidst the Bamboo Forest
(Source: Re:public Inc.)

Figure 11: Prototype Study: Exploring the Flexibility of Bamboo
(Source: Re:public Inc.)

Figure 12: "Designing Structural Elements: 3D Modeling Bamboo Joints"
(Source: Masaaki Iwamoto Laboratory, Kyushu University.)

Figure 13: Collaborative Construction: Students and Experts Building a Bamboo Shelter
(Source: Re:public Inc.)

Figure 14: Showcasing Bamboo Architecture: Final Event with the Local Community
(Source: Re:public Inc.)

4 Bamboo Architecture: Economy for the Future of Satsumasendai City

Satsumasendai City faces the challenge of transitioning its economy away from reliance on the nuclear plants, which currently provide the majority of jobs and economic activity (fig 15). As the nuclear industry diminishes in the coming decades, it is crucial to explore new avenues for economic growth and job

creation, particularly for the future generations residing in Satsumasendai. Bamboo architecture presents a promising opportunity to not only address this challenge but also foster a new green economy and sustainable development for the city. The concept of a bamboo architecture economy goes beyond simply utilizing bamboo as a building material. It encompasses the entire process, from the management of abandoned bamboo forests to the creation of innovative bamboo-based architectural designs. By effectively managing these neglected bamboo resources, new green jobs can be generated, and a range of expertise connected to bamboo architecture can emerge. This includes bamboo cultivation, harvesting, processing, and construction techniques, which require specialized knowledge and skills. The development of these new job opportunities and expertise will contribute to the local economy and provide employment opportunities for the residents of Satsumasendai. Furthermore, embracing bamboo architecture can position Satsumasendai City as a hub for innovative and sustainable construction practices. Bamboo, with its rapid growth and sustainable qualities, offers a renewable and environmentally friendly alternative to traditional building materials. By incorporating bamboo into architectural designs, the city can showcase its commitment to sustainability, attracting attention and interest from visitors and investors alike. This can lead to increased tourism, investment in bamboo-related industries, and the establishment of research and development centers focused on bamboo architecture. Satsumasendai City has the potential to become a pioneer in bamboo-based construction, setting an example for other cities and inspiring a broader movement toward sustainable urban development.

The shift towards a bamboo architecture economy not only provides economic benefits but also contributes to the overall resilience and sustainability of the city. Bamboo forests, once neglected and posing risks, can be transformed into valuable assets that enhance the local environment and ecosystem. By actively managing and utilizing these bamboo resources, Satsumasendai City can mitigate the risks of disasters such as landslides, while promoting biodiversity and restoring natural habitats. This holistic approach aligns with the principles of sustainable development, ensuring a harmonious relationship between human activities and the environment. The implementation of a bamboo architecture economy in Satsumasendai City offers a transformative pathway towards a resilient and prosperous future. By managing abandoned bamboo forests, creating green jobs, fostering expertise in bamboo architecture, and embracing sustainable construction practices, the city can establish a new economic sector that promotes innovation, environmental stewardship, and community well-being. Satsumasendai City has the potential to lead the way in sustainable urban development, serving as a model for other communities and contributing to a greener and more sustainable future.

Figure 15: Bird's-eye view of Satsumasendai City with Nuclear Plant
(Source: Google Earth obtained in July 2023)

The Satsuma Future Commons (SFC) project aims to bring about systemic city changes, similar to the transformative impact seen in Bali's Green School. Just as the Green School has revolutionized eco-ethical design and cooperative living, the SFC project seeks to foster a sustainable and vibrant city by integrating bamboo architecture and green principles. By emulating the success of the Green School, the SFC project envisions a future where bamboo becomes a driving force for economic growth, innovation, and job creation in Satsumasendai City. Through the establishment of bamboo-related industries and the cultivation of local expertise, the city can position itself as a leader in the green economy, attracting investment and collaboration to ensure a resilient and sustainable future. The adoption of the green concept in building design and its impact on creating a sustainable environment has been widely recognized (Alimin et al., 2021). By incorporating green design principles and creating an eco-environment, schools can cultivate intentional habits and foster environmentally-conscious communities. Sustainable architecture and eco-friendly practices, such as using bamboo in construction, utilizing renewable energy sources, recycling waste, and implementing organic gardening, create an environment that encourages students to embrace green principles and develop a sustainable mindset. The transformative potential of sustainable architecture and an eco-friendly environment in promoting familiarity with and commitment to environmentally-friendly concepts is evident.

5 Bamboo and Spatial Design: Creating Harmony between Humanity and Nature

Biophilic design is a concept used within the building industry to increase occupant connectivity to the natural environment through the use of direct nature, indirect nature, and space and place conditions (Kellert, 2008). Biophilic design aims to enhance the connection between people and nature by incorporating natural elements and patterns into the built environment. Bamboo, being a natural and renewable material, has inherent qualities that align with the principles of biophilic design. When bamboo is used as a building material, it brings the essence of nature into the constructed space. Its organic texture, patterns, and colors create a visually appealing and soothing environment, evoking a sense of being connected to the natural world. Furthermore, bamboo structures can provide opportunities for direct and indirect contact with nature. The presence of bamboo within architectural spaces can create a sense of immersion in nature, promoting a calming and restorative atmosphere. Additionally, bamboo can be used strategically to allow for the penetration of natural light, ventilation, and views of the surrounding landscape, further enhancing the connection to the natural environment. The use of bamboo in building design also aligns with the principles of sustainability and environmental stewardship, which are inherent to biophilic design. Bamboo is a rapidly renewable resource with a low environmental footprint, making it an eco-friendly alternative to traditional building materials. By incorporating bamboo into architectural structures, BambooScape promotes sustainable practices and a closer relationship with nature. In summary, BambooScape's focus on using bamboo as a building material aligns with the principles of biophilic design by fostering a stronger connection between occupants and the natural environment. The incorporation of bamboo in architectural spaces enhances visual, tactile, and sensory experiences, creating a harmonious and biophilic living environment (Fig 16). One positive aspect of biophilic design, particularly in the context of resilient futures, is its potential to improve the well-being and resilience of individuals and communities. By incorporating elements of nature into the built environment, biophilic design can contribute to the physical and mental health of occupants, ultimately enhancing their ability to adapt and thrive in the face of challenges and disruptions. Biophilic design has been found to have numerous benefits, including stress reduction, increased productivity, improved cognitive function, and enhanced overall well-being (Browning et al., 2014). These outcomes are especially relevant in the context of resilience, as they can help individuals and communities better cope with and recover from shocks and stresses, such as natural disasters, climate change impacts, or social disruptions. Moreover, biophilic design can create spaces that promote connection, social cohesion, and community engagement (Beatley, 2011). By incorporating natural elements and creating inviting outdoor spaces, it encourages people to interact and form stronger social bonds, fostering a sense of belonging and collective resilience. This social aspect of biophilic design can support communities in coming together, sharing resources, and collectively

adapting to changing circumstances. In terms of physical resilience, biophilic design can contribute to energy efficiency and resource conservation. Natural ventilation, daylighting strategies, and green infrastructure can help reduce energy consumption and mitigate the impacts of extreme weather events. Incorporating vegetation and green spaces into urban areas can also provide cooling effects, reduce the urban heat island effect, and improve air quality, thereby enhancing the resilience of communities to climate-related risks. Overall, biophilic design offers a positive aspect in resilient futures by creating environments that promote human well-being, foster social cohesion, and enhance physical resilience. By reconnecting people with nature and integrating natural elements into the built environment, biophilic design contributes to creating sustainable, adaptable, and thriving communities in the face of future challenges.

Figure 16: Biophilic green urban design elements in cities (Hidalgo, Ana. 2014).

6 Circular Economy in the BambooScope Project: Embracing Sustainable Material Life Cycles

The concepts of circular economy and circular design are integral to the sustainable practices and principles embraced by the BambooScope project (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2012). By adopting circular principles, the project aims to minimize waste, maximize resource efficiency, and promote the longevity of bamboo materials, thereby contributing to a more sustainable and regenerative approach to architecture and design. Circular economy is an economic system that aims to eliminate waste and promote the continual use of resources through closed-loop systems (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017). It emphasizes the importance of reusing, recycling, and repurposing materials to minimize resource extraction and environmental impact. Circular design, on the other hand, focuses on designing products and systems with the intention of reducing waste and ensuring that materials can be easily disassembled,

recycled, or repurposed at the end of their lifecycle (Braungart & McDonough, 2002). The BambooScape project incorporates circular economy and circular design principles in various ways. Firstly, the project promotes the use of closed-loop systems, where bamboo materials are recycled and reused within the project itself. For example, when bamboo structures or pavilions reach the end of their lifespan, the bamboo can be disassembled, and the materials can be repurposed or recycled to create new structures or products. This approach minimizes waste and reduces the demand for new bamboo resources. Additionally, the project recognizes the value of bamboo charcoal as a second life for bamboo used in architecture. Bamboo charcoal contains a significantly higher amount of mineral components such as potassium and sodium compared to wood charcoal. It is also highly porous, which gives it excellent soil improvement and deodorizing effects. As a result, bamboo charcoal is increasingly being utilized as a soil amendment and deodorizer. By exploring the utilization of bamboo charcoal, the BambooScape project further enhances the circular economy process by repurposing bamboo waste into valuable products with various applications. Life cycle thinking is another key component of circular design embraced by the BambooScape project. It involves considering the entire life cycle of bamboo materials, from sourcing to disposal, and optimizing each stage for sustainability. By taking into account the environmental and social impacts of bamboo production, processing, and usage, the project can make informed decisions to minimize negative effects and maximize positive outcomes. Life cycle thinking ensures that the project considers the full impact of its actions and strives to achieve sustainability throughout the bamboo material's life cycle. Recycling of processed bamboo used in architecture is an essential aspect of the BambooScape project's circular approach. Bamboo, as a highly renewable and versatile material, can be recycled and repurposed for various applications. For instance, bamboo culms can be transformed into composite materials, such as bamboo fiberboards or laminated bamboo panels, which can be used in construction, furniture, and other industries. By recycling processed bamboo and exploring additional uses such as bamboo charcoal, the project reduces the need for virgin materials, minimizes waste generation, and promotes resource efficiency. Incorporating circular economy principles into the design and construction processes of the BambooScape project is crucial for achieving its sustainability goals. This includes selecting sustainable bamboo sources, optimizing material use, and ensuring that the design allows for disassembly, reusability, and recycling. By considering the entire life cycle of bamboo materials and integrating circular principles from the outset, the project can minimize its environmental footprint, reduce resource consumption, and contribute to a more sustainable built environment. The BambooScape project serves as a model for circular economy and circular design in the context of bamboo architecture and spatial design. By promoting closed-loop systems, life cycle thinking, and the recycling of processed bamboo, including the exploration of bamboo charcoal, the project showcases how circular principles can be integrated into sustainable construction practices. By embracing these principles, the BambooScape project not only minimizes waste and resource consumption but also inspires a shift towards more sustainable and regenerative design practices within the architectural and construction industry.

6.1 Circular Economy Experiment: Bamboo Charcoal Fertilizer for Community Garden

In addition to incorporating circular economy and circular design principles, the Satsuma Future Commons (SFC) project has actively experimented with circular practices using bamboo. One notable initiative involved the creation of a community garden where bamboo charcoal was utilized as a sustainable fertilizer, demonstrating the project's commitment to resource efficiency and community engagement. The experiment began by sourcing abandoned bamboo from local bamboo forests in Satsumasendai (Fig. 16). The bamboo was carefully selected and processed to produce bamboo charcoal (Fig. 17). The conversion process involved heating the bamboo under controlled conditions to remove moisture and volatile substances, resulting in a highly porous and mineral-rich charcoal product. The bamboo charcoal was then used as a natural fertilizer to enrich the soil in the community garden (Fig. 18). Its high porosity and mineral content enhanced soil quality, improving nutrient retention and water absorption capabilities. This sustainable fertilizer not only provided essential nutrients for plant growth but also helped regulate soil pH and microbial activity.

Community engagement played a vital role in this circular economy experiment. Local residents, project participants, and volunteers joined forces to plant and cultivate various crops in the community garden (Fig. 19). The garden became a collaborative space where knowledge sharing, hands-on learning, and teamwork flourished. Through regular maintenance, watering, and harvesting, the community actively participated in the sustainable cultivation practices promoted by the SFC project. The community garden in Satsumasendai became a focal point for fostering a sense of community and environmental stewardship. It provided a space for residents to reconnect with nature, learn about sustainable gardening techniques, and cultivate a closer relationship with the land. The garden not only yielded fresh, locally grown produce but also served as a platform for exchanging ideas, promoting healthy lifestyles, and strengthening social bonds among community members (Fig. 20). The circular economy experiment with bamboo charcoal fertilizer in the community garden demonstrated the potential for sustainable resource utilization and community empowerment. By repurposing abandoned bamboo, transforming it into valuable charcoal, and utilizing it as a nutrient-rich fertilizer, the project exemplified the principles of circularity and resource efficiency. Moreover, the active involvement of the community in the garden activities fostered a sense of ownership, collaboration, and shared responsibility, further strengthening the project's impact and promoting sustainable habits within the local community. Through initiatives like the community garden, the BambooScape project and the SFC project continue to showcase the practical application of circular economy principles and their positive influence on community well-being. These endeavors emphasize the importance of engaging communities, promoting sustainable practices, and creating spaces that inspire and empower individuals to embrace sustainable living and environmental stewardship.

Fig. 16: Abandoned Bamboo Harvested from Local Bamboo Forest (Source: Re:public Inc.)

Fig. 17: Bamboo Charcoal Production Process (Source: Re:public Inc.)

Fig. 18: Application of Bamboo Charcoal Fertilizer in the Community Garden (Source: Re:public Inc.)

Fig. 19: Community Members Planting and Caring for the Garden (Source: Re:public Inc.)

Fig. 20: Community Engagement in the Satsumasendai Community Garden (Source: Re:public Inc.)

7 Conclusion and next steps

The BambooScape project within the Satsuma Future Commons (SFC) initiative has demonstrated the transformative potential of bamboo in sustainable architecture and spatial design. By embracing Circular Design principles, the project has showcased how bamboo can contribute to ecological balance, minimize environmental impact, and promote sustainable and regenerative practices. Through sustainable forest management, the BambooScape project has addressed the pressing issue of abandoned bamboo forests, promoting responsible resource utilization and ecosystem preservation. By incorporating bamboo as a primary building material, the project has harnessed its rapid growth, versatility, and sustainability, offering an eco-friendly alternative to traditional construction materials. Furthermore, the BambooScape project has fostered the development of a bamboo architecture economy, creating new green jobs, attracting investment, and positioning Satsumasendai City as a leader in sustainable and innovative construction practices. The integration of biophilic design principles has enhanced the connection between occupants and nature, promoting well-being, social cohesion, and physical resilience. By adopting circular economy principles, the project has minimized waste, maximized resource efficiency, and explored new life cycles for bamboo, such as the utilization of bamboo charcoal. The BambooScape project serves as a model for circular economy and circular design, inspiring a shift towards more sustainable and regenerative practices within the architectural and construction industry. Overall, the BambooScape project aims to raise national awareness and set an example of a sustainable city with a new ecosystem. It emphasizes the significant potential of bamboo in construction, highlighting its versatility, eco-friendliness, and ability to contribute to a greener and more sustainable future. By showcasing the success of the project, it is hoped that more cities and communities will embrace bamboo as a viable and sustainable building material, promoting a harmonious coexistence between humanity and nature.

References

- Alimin, Nurhayatu & Pertiwi, E & Purwaningrum, Lulu. (2021). Establishing sustainable habits of students in Green School Bali through green interior design. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. 905. 012075. 10.1088/1755-1315/905/1/012075.
- Beatley, T. (2011). Biophilic cities: Integrating nature into urban design and planning. Island Press.
- Braungart, M., & McDonough, W. (2002). Cradle to cradle: Remaking the way we make things. North Point Press.

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- Browning, W. D., Ryan, C. O., & Clancy, J. O. (2014). 14 patterns of biophilic design: Improving health and well-being in the built environment. Terrapin Bright Green.
- Dumitrescu, L., Bliuc, I., Baran, I., Pescaru, R.-A. & Parincu, P.-D. (2023). Regenerative Design - General Principles and Implementation Strategies in Building Design. Bulletin of the Polytechnic Institute of Iași. Construction. Architecture Section. 67. 1-21. 10.2478/bipca-2021-0031.
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2012). Towards the circular economy: Economic and business rationale for an accelerated transition.
- Geissdoerfer, M., Savaget, P., Bocken, N. M., & Hultink, E. J. (2017). The Circular Economy—A new sustainability paradigm? Journal of Cleaner Production, 143, 757-768.
- Gupta, Anu & Kumar, Ajit. (2008). Potential of Bamboo in Sustainable Development Asia-Pacific Business Review. IV. 100-107.
- Hidalgo, Ana. (2014). Biophilic Design, Restorative Environments and Well-Being. 9th International Conference on Design and Emotion 2014: The Colors of Care
- Kellert, S. R. (2008). The biophilia hypothesis. Island Press.
- Takashi Someya, Shion Takemura, Shun Miyamoto, Mahito Kamada, (2010) "Predictions of bamboo forest distribution and associated environmental factors in Japan, using natural environmental information GIS and digital national land information" Landscape Ecology
https://www.istage.ist.go.jp/article/jale/15/2/15_2_41/pdf/-char/ja
- The Natural Environment Symbiosis Technology Association (2019), "Technologies and Cases Contributing to Adaptation to Climate Change in the Field of Natural Environment"
http://www.necta.jp/pdf/adptec_all.pdf